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SILICE: A prototype of a national scholarly information system based on open sources¹

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Introduction

Scientific evaluation systems are ever more based on bibliometric indicators, because they require objective, fast and auditable procedures (Moed, 2020). Traditionally, this information has been supplied by commercial citation indexes. The reason of such dependence is that the extraction and processing of citations required a great economic and organizational effort, and only a few number of large companies would compute this information. However, this fact generates a data dependence on private companies that may cause lack of independence, or even worst, biases in evaluation processes (Jappe, 2020). For example, these service can limit their coverage to specific journals, document types or languages according to commercial and not as much to quality criteria (Mongeon, & Paul-Hus, 2016). This would cause an under- or overvaluation of researchers and organizations, distorting their research performance.

However, in the recent years, advances in the standardization, processing and storage (*Big data*) of bibliographic citations have encouraged the creation of new and alternative citation indexes. On one hand, the free releasing of bibliographic references by publishers through Crossref (Martín-Martín, 2021), and, on the other hand, the automatic extraction of citations by new academic search engines, is increasing the availability of citation data that can be freely reused for alternative projects (Ortega, 2014).

This communication aims to present a new prototype of national scholarly information system (SILICE) based on open sources, with the purpose of demonstrating that it is possible to create *ad hoc* information systems apart from commercial platforms, with a much more reduced cost and adaptable to each particular environment.

SILICE (Sistema de Información para la Literatura Científica Española) is a beta web application (web site) that attempts to gather the scholarly production of both Spanish researchers and organizations, including citations and altmetric mentions to these publications. The system is structured in several modules that illustrate the outputs and associated metrics of each entity. These entities are: publications, authors, organizations and disciplines.

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Data

Data are the main elements of this application and they are obtained from a varied range of open sources that allows the reuse of data freely (CC0) or with attribution (CC-BY).

Figure 1. Data, entities (rectangles) and sources (ellipses) scheme

Two different strategies were used to obtain the most reliable collection of the Spanish research publications: a set from authors and a set from affiliations. This double strategy is due to the double need to gather the total production of Spanish authors, wherever it is produced; and the total production of Spanish organizations, independent of the origin of their researchers. Another problem is related to the mobility of researchers, who can produce publications in different organizations. For these reasons, it is not possible to assume organizations as an aggregated of authors.

Publications from authors

This strategy selects publications through authors and allows us to build the list of author profiles. In this manner, authors IDs for three different sources are processed to create a consolidated list of authors:

- **ORCID:** this is the principal open author identifier and ever more required in Spanish assessment exercises. Then, we assume that most of the profiles have a ORCID code. 320k Spanish profiles were estimated. However, sometimes this identifier does not have assigned an affiliation or it is not update. In those cases, other sources were used to consolidate these profiles.
- **Google Scholar Citations:** Ranking of researchers in Spain and Spaniards abroad (<https://www.webometrics.info/en/GoogleScholar/Spain>) is a curated list of Google Scholar Citations profiles from Spanish authors. This ranking developed by the Cybermetric Labs of the CSIC has the advantage of that the ranking is refined with correct affiliations, complete names and gender. It includes more than 100k profiles.
- **OpenAlex:** It is taking the baton of Microsoft Academic, curating and enlarging the repository of this disappeared search engine. It includes more than 926k profiles connected to publications. Its main drawback is the duplicity of profiles.

Once processed the list of authors with their different identifiers linked to each profile (ORCID, OpenAlexID, etc.), we have retrieved the list of publications of each profile using the DOI of each publication. Several sources were used to extract this dataset:

- Crossref: It is the organization that assigns the DOI to each publication and it makes public the complete database of all the publications with a DOI. This database is created from the direct contribution of the associated publishers. Its main drawback is that many of these records are deposited without curation and some data may lack of affiliations, references, etc., (Hendricks et al., 2020).
- OpenAlex: This database also allows the open use of their bibliographic information and it provides a free endpoint to extract their data. Its main advantage is their coverage and curation of their data with links to several identifiers that help to consolidated the information (Chawla, 2022).
- Semantic Scholar: This is an academic search engine that offers their database openly with attribution. This source is used to complete the information of the other sources because it has an important coverage of web publications (repositories, conference proceedings, open access journals, etc.) (Lo et al., 2019).

Publications from organizations

This second strategy searches publications using the affiliation, filtering papers that include Spain or España in the address. Crossref and Open Alex enable to search by affiliation and therefore were used to gather this set of publications. The main drawback of this procedure is that could have a high proportion of records without affiliation field or not completely filled. These affiliations were processed and normalized according to the Research Organization Registry (RoR) to create the entity Organizations.

These two datasets were merged in a central repository of publications, which constitutes the core of scientific outputs of the Spanish science system. This database approximately includes 2M of publications.

Metrics

A research assessment tool requires to include metrics that permit the valuation of their research outputs. SILICE includes a large range of metrics associated to publications, mainly bibliographic citations and altmetric mentions:

Citations: Traditional citations indexes calculate their citations from the references included in their databases, causing that the citing and cited publications come from the same place. Hence, to compute a high number of citations, the system requires the most comprehensive database of scientific literature (Garfield, 2006). However, this is not efficient for a system that is specialized in local scientific literature, because we would need 300M of publications with their references to compute citations for only 2M of publications. This prototype attempts to solve this limitation searching in several platforms that allows to retrieve only the list of citations to each document from our database:

- Semantic Scholar: This search engine provides through its API the possibility to search publications and retrieve their citations from its database. These citations are automatically processed and extracted by the search engine.
- OpenAlex: This platform recovers the Microsoft Academic Graph and its citation repository. It also makes possible to find the citations to a specific document. In this case, DOIs have to be converted to OpenAlexID to obtain the list of citations.
- Crossref Open Citation Index (COCI): Crossref offers publishers the option to openly deposit the references of their publications. Today, most of the commercial publishers,

included Elsevier, are freely depositing this information, being publicly accessible through Crossref API. However, this service does not compute the citations to each document, this option is only for their partners. Because the information is open, a non-profit foundation committed with the open citation movement, OpenCitations, has indeed created a citation index from this information. COCI uses Linked data technology to create a doi-to-doi database that can be used to design open citation indexes (Heibi et al., 2019).

Next, a general repository of citations was created from these sources, including only citations to Spanish publications. In this manner, the size of the citation repository (no more than 500M) is much smaller than the expected for a general citation index, with billions of citations.

Altmetrics: alternative metrics show a different view about the publication impact, counting the mentions from web platforms (social networks, blogs, news, official documents, etc.) with the aim of capturing the impact in external environments (public opinion, education, government, media, etc.) apart from the scholarly world. There are several altmetric data providers that gather these mentions, but only two make publicly available their data: Altmetric.com and Crossref Event Data (CED). These mentions were used to complete the impact of publications, authors and organizations.

- **Altmetric.com**: this is one of the most comprehensive altmetric providers, with an important coverage of social networks and media mentions. It offers a public API to extract the count of mentions from the DOI of each document (Ortega, 2020).
- **CED**: it is a service from Crossref and it gathers no aggregated “events” about publications. It stands out in Wikipedia citations.

Disciplines

This last part is more complex and it aims to classify the documents by the main research areas and presents a framework of the most important organizations, authors and publications in each area. Three sources were used to perform this classification:

- **OpenAlex**: This platform maintains the Microsoft Academic’s conceptual framework. This system assigns labels to each paper according to the content of the abstract. This system is hierarchical, which makes possible to group the papers in large disciplinary areas. However, the automatic assignation of concepts can cause some misreading.
- **Crossref**: Some publisher partners include subjects for their publications. They use All Subject Journal Classification (ASJC) to classify the publications, an extended classification scheme. This classification is done about the journal of the publication.
- **Altmetric.com**: this data provider also includes information about the subject matter of the publication and uses ASJC as well.

Conclusions

This description of the data structure and the sources implemented in SILICE prototype attempts to evidence the real possibility of creating custom citations indexes that fit with the research evaluation requirements, supplying specific data about the production and impact of the scientific literature in particular places or organizations. This proposal makes evident the need of creating services that do not depend on external criteria or metrics that could distort the performance or the appreciation of intrinsic scientific traditions.

The main originality of this proposal is that it is entirely based on open sources that can be freely used with/without attribution, which allows to customize any element in the system and

to critically select the most suitable sources according to the requirements and needs of the system.

Another important innovation is that the citation repository is independent from the publication dataset, which permits to compute the global impact of publications, authors and organizations, without losing the global context of the Spanish scientific literature.

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